

VET for all: Assessing the case of Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

Presenting a case study of Bangladesh, this article contributes to our understanding of how VET has expanded in LMICs, and how this process has been shaped by global efforts to improve VET's accessibility. The analysis draws on historical institutionalism and the work of Margaret Archer, and is based on policy document analysis and the interpretation of quantitative and qualitative data. The article concludes that, even when it is weakly linked to the labor market, formal VET expands because of the actions of key policy actors and societal demand for formal qualifications that signal *academic*, rather than *vocational*, competence.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the promotion of vocational education and training (VET) has once again become a central goal of education policy the world over, and in low and medium income countries (LMICs) in particular – most notably through the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) (Allais and Wedekind, 2020; United Nations, 2015). With this, VET has experienced a remarkable renaissance. Since the early 1990s, it had been sidelined in the global development policy discourse, which favored basic education; the World Bank had assumed that poverty would be more likely to be reduced by improving access to primary education in particular (Psacharopoulos, 1987; World Bank, 1991). However, more than a decade later, with the financial crisis of 2007/08 exacerbating youth unemployment, policy makers started to be convinced that VET could make an important contribution to poverty reduction, by helping the poorest gain access to decent employment and income (ILO, 2012b; King and Palmer, 2007; UNESCO, 2012). In this context the United Nations (2015) formulated the goal of "ensuring equal access for all women and men to affordable and quality technical, vocational and tertiary education", as part of the SDGs.

The current development policy approach to VET – referred to here as "VET for all" – differs from the approach of earlier decades. From the 1960 s, VET was promoted primarily for economic development, by providing a skilled workforce for critical industries (Abrokwa, 1995). Clearly, achieving this economic policy goal was riddled with difficulties; Foster's (1965) "vocational school fallacy" pointed to the low attractiveness of VET, because higher status jobs in LMICs were all

awarded on the basis of university degrees. Even today, there is much evidence that the current more socio-political goals of VET in LMICs are not being achieved (UNESCO, 2021, pp. 255–258), and that Foster's thesis is still relevant; Allais and Wedekind (2020), for example, refer to the lack of "labor market opportunity structures" that could boost social demand for VET.

Although such findings make an important contribution to understanding VET in LMICs, they hardly ever systematically examine how and why VET systems in these countries develop over time. Yet, it is precisely this long-term perspective on VET development that is needed to understand why the goal of "VET for all" is so difficult to achieve. Instead, what can be described as a "deficit-oriented" view prevails in theory formation, explaining challenges in LMICs' VET systems in terms of what they *lack* (compared to more established VET systems), such as "labor market opportunity structures" or structures that, as Doner and Schneider (2016, p. 5) propose, could support "coordination among state agencies, among firms, and between public and private actors". We are suggesting that VET system development should be analyzed in terms of *existing* factors – not just *missing* factors. We believe that this has been done in a productive way for economically developed countries in recent years (see e.g., Bonoli and Emmenegger, 2022; Busemeyer and Trampusch, 2012; Thelen, 2004). While these studies are increasingly registered in the literature on VET in LMICs (Allais and Wedekind, 2020; Valiente et al., 2021), it remains unclear whether OECD country studies add much value to our understanding of VET in LMICs.

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1.1. Aims of the case study

In order to contribute to our understanding of how VET systems in LMICs develop, and why they often fail to deliver on the promise of "VET for all", this article presents findings from a case study of Bangladesh. This case is relevant, firstly, from a development policy perspective: at independence from Pakistan in the 1970s, Bangladesh was considered a "basket case", characterized by extreme poverty, weak infrastructure and a lack of economic growth, which – in conjunction with its large population – meant the country became a major recipient of development aid (Baxter, 1997; Faaland, 1981). Since then, it has come to be considered a lower middle-income country, as a consequence of strong economic growth, notably in the garment industry (Berg et al., 2021; Rahman, 2001; World Bank, 2016). Secondly, Bangladesh's educational development seems to mirror global aid trends: for example, from the 1980s onwards, primary education was greatly expanded with considerable international support, a process that intensified in the years of the global "Education for All" campaign (Dove, 1983; Jalaluddin and Chowdhury, 1997; World Bank, 2000); and in 2011, the very years in which VET experienced a renaissance at the global level, policy makers initiated a comprehensive reform of VET in Bangladesh, which aimed at improving access to VET for the poorest (Ministry of Education, 2011) using instruments from the "VET policy toolbox" (McGrath, 2012), including competency-based training, a qualifications framework and recognition of prior learning (RPL) schemes. Thirdly, the development of VET in Bangladesh has only rarely been discussed in the global literature (Haolader et al., 2017; Maurer, 2012), while the developments in other parts of South Asia, notably in India, have received far more attention (see e.g. Agrawal and Agrawal, 2017; Maitra and Maitra, 2019; Maitra et al., 2022; Sharma and King, 2019).

Against this backdrop, this paper addresses three interrelated questions:

- How has VET in Bangladesh developed since the 2011 reforms, in terms of institutional change, quantitative expansion, and its relation to the labor market?
- What influence have donors had on these developments, and to what degree has their ambition to widen access to VET been implemented?
- How can these developments be explained – and how do these explanations complement existing findings in the literature?

The paper uses an analytical framework inspired by historical institutionalism (Stefes, 2019; Thelen, 2002) and the work of Margaret Archer (1979, 1982a), both of which are described in more detail further below. Historical institutionalism examines institutional change as an interdependent relationship between institutions (or structures) and actors, and has recently been taken up by political science studies on the development of VET systems in comparatively economically developed countries (Busemeyer and Trampusch, 2012; Graf, 2021; Thelen, 2004). Archer's (1979, 1982a) approach, which similarly focuses on the relationship between institutions (or structures) and actors, complements the historical institutionalist perspective by assuming that the development of education systems follows a logic that unfolds in phases, and focusing less on the political-economic actors who are at the center of most historical-institutionalist analyses, and more on other actors who only emerge in the course of educational development.

1.2. Methodological approach

In terms of methodology, the article is based four types of data that allow to analyze and interpret the institutional development of VET in Bangladesh:

Firstly, there are text documents, in particular policy documents authored by public authorities or donors. These documents allow us to map institutional change with regard to key VET reforms, as well as the attitudes of specific corporate actors, from the period between

Bangladesh's independence to the reforms around 2011. Many of these documents were collected during extensive research between 2006 and 2008 (see Maurer, 2011), while access to the documents on the 2011 reform was made possible through regular exchanges with policy makers in this particular period.

Secondly, there are 34 qualitative interviews, which were conducted within the framework of a comparative multi-country research project in 2021 and 2022 (and are referenced with the abbreviation "Int", e.g., "Int 1"). 12 of the interviews were conducted with representatives of authorities (Int 1–12), 18 with training providers (Int 13–30) and 4 with association representatives (Int 31–34). While the qualitative interviews with the authorities and the training providers aimed to understand the implementation of the 2011 reform, the interviews with the associations served to analyze the current significance of formal VET qualifications in the labor market. These two types of data form the basis of the main part of this paper and were analyzed using qualitative content analysis (Gläser and Laudel, 2019; Kuckartz, 2018). In the analysis, it had to be taken into account that interview partners would tend to represent implementation processes in a socially desirable way – which is why a triangulation with statistical data from the country's official educational statistics (BANBEIS, 2023) was useful, which represented the third data category and in some cases even formed the starting point of the qualitative interviews.

Fourthly, there are data from a survey of 161 companies in the ready-made garment and pharmaceutical industries (conducted as part of the international research project mentioned above, with key findings synthesized elsewhere; see Kalam and Shimu, 2020; Shimu, 2021). These data serve to understand the importance of different educational qualifications in the formal part of the labor market and thus complement the qualitative interviews with industry associations mentioned above.

2. Theoretical background

2.1. The comparative literature on VET in LMICs

As the role of VET in development policy has been a matter of great controversy for decades, it has come under the scrutiny of scholars in a range of different disciplines. The debate has long been influenced by the economics of education scholarship, much of which has tried to assess the economic value added by VET, in particular by utilizing the human capital approach that dominated the field from the 1980s onwards (Becker, 1962; Psacharopoulos, 1987; Psacharopoulos and Loxley, 1985; Sobel, 1978). In light of these studies' findings, the World Bank, which had been heavily involved in VET financing from the 1960 onwards, turned away from it towards the end of the 1980s, to focus mainly on primary education (World Bank, 1980, 1991, 1995). However, the debate has also been central to more sociological approaches to comparative education, which analyze VET (and increasingly vocational skill formation more generally) in within the broader societal contexts of LMICs, whilst still taking into consideration the impact of global factors (Allais, 2012; Benavot, 1983; McGrath et al., 2020). It was also mainly the sociologically-informed comparative literature on VET in LMICs that incorporated political science insights on skill formation in economically more developed countries (Hall and Soskice, 2001; Lauder et al., 2008; Thelen, 2004).

The problem addressed in this article – how VET systems develop in LMICs – is rarely examined in a systematic way. The starting point of many analyses is the identification of certain challenges to the development of VET, the causes of which are then investigated. Allais and Wedekind (2020), who are representative of this approach, point to four strongly interrelated core challenges: firstly, often only a small proportion of learners take vocational programs, despite the political prioritization of VET; secondly, the quality of education is low, often due to a lack of infrastructure or underqualified teachers; thirdly, many VET graduates do not find employment; fourthly, VET has a low social standing.

While research and policy-oriented reports tend to concur on the key challenges facing VET, (see e.g., Arias et al., 2019; UNESCO, 2012, 2017), their explanations of causes differ significantly, depending on their theoretical position. Three positions will be briefly outlined here:

One position that has long dominated comparative education and continues to influence the interpretation of the development of VET systems today (though often less explicitly), is that of functionalism (Eisenstadt, 1995; Hans, 1964; Smelser, 1985). Authors whose perspectives can be characterized as functionalist argue that VET in LMICs develops as a function of economic structures and in close alignment with the labor market. Ashton et al. (2000), for instance, suggest that public TVET systems had developed in many LMICs shortly after independence because they were considered important for the "state-led centralized systems of economic development," but that economic liberalization in the 1980s led to a "disjuncture", that is, a growth of mostly private training schemes on the one hand, geared to the booming export economy, and an increase in public TVET institutions on the other hand, to correct "market failures" so that workers in informal labor markets and the unemployed could access training, too. Foster's (1965) "vocational school fallacy" thesis, mentioned above, can also be seen as functionalist. Foster argued that the disinterest of young people in vocational training was rational, because, in the *existing* labor markets – not those that should have been created according to industrial plans – the majority of attractive jobs were for graduates of higher education. This argument can also be found in studies whose perspective cannot be labelled as functionalist, such as those by Allais and Wedekind (2020) and Schneider and Karcher (2010), the latter using the example of Latin America to illustrate institutional complementarities in the labor market that hinder the development of an effective vocational training system.

In contrast to the functionalist position, classical neo-Marxist analyses explain the transformation of VET systems not in terms of the functional needs of the economy and the labor market, but in terms of the conflicting interests of social groups (Bowles and Gintis, 1976; Cole, 2007; Livingstone, 1995). With regard to VET in LMICs, a central argument of this literature is that the dominant classes promote it as a means to channel the lower classes to the less prestigious segments of labor markets, thus restricting access to higher-status education that enables wealthier students to enter the upper echelons of the world of work (Bacchus, 1988). These contributions argue that policy makers promote VET in response to perceived threats of "overeducation" (Abrokwa, 1995; Irizarry, 1980). Yet, some representatives of the neo-Marxist perspective have also emphasized the importance of VET to fundamental economic and social change (Ergas, 1982).

A third important position in the analysis of VET in LMICs is influenced by postcolonial theory, notably Allais and Wedekind's (2020) reading of global target setting in VET. From this perspective, education and training in LMICs can only be understood within the broader post-colonial context of these countries. Firstly, existing political and economic structures and dominant cultural ideas in LMICs still reflect the power structures of the colonial period. Secondly, the situation in LMIC labor markets mirrors the economic dependence of these countries and their disadvantaged positions in the global division of labor. Thirdly, the priorities of education policy in many LMICs are very much shaped by international organizations and a global discourse that is currently represented by the SDGs, which often lead governments and authorities in these countries to engage in "policy posturing".

2.2. This article's theoretical approach

This case study on Bangladesh takes a different theoretical approach, to overcome the limitations of the above perspectives. The starting point for the present analysis is a heuristic model informed by historical institutionalism, which examines social change with a view to the reciprocal relationship between institutions and actors (Stefes, 2019; Thelen, 2002). Proponents of this approach argue that comprehensive institutional change, i.e., critical junctures, are often caused by external

shocks that initiate a new path of development, which shapes the subsequent reproduction of institutions through path-dependent effects. This reproduction is supported on the one hand by positive feedback from actors who benefit from these institutions, and on the other hand by complementarities with other institutions, possibly even in other policy areas. A major contribution of the historical institutionalist literature also lies in pointing to different forms of incremental institutional change, and examining them in more detail, distinguishing in particular between transformative and self-preserving institutional change (see e.g., Trampusch, 2010). Historical institutionalism has been frequently applied in analyses of skill formation systems, especially since Thelen's (2004) seminal work on the "political economy of skills" in Germany, Britain, the United States, and Japan, which showed how skills development was shaped by the relationship between state actors and different groups of employers and employees. Now, many of these works are indeed helpful in explaining different forms of institutional change in skill formation, case by case (Busemeyer and Trampusch, 2012; Graf, 2021; Thelen, 2004). Yet, their ambitions are different from those of authoritative comparative educationists, who have attempted to create *macrosociological* (functionalist or neo-Marxist) models of change in educational systems, assuming that such change, whilst taking country-specific forms, follows some universal principles worldwide (Bowles and Gintis, 1976; Hans, 1964; Smelser, 1985).

An intermediate position with respect to these ambitions is taken by Margaret Archer, in her work on the growth of educational systems (Archer, 1979, 1982a), which has been revived in comparative education in recent years (see e.g., Powell and McGrath, 2019; Schriewer, 2021) and will serve as a second important theoretical basis for this case study. Archer assumes that the growth of educational systems does not follow a logic, but does exhibit "regularities" across countries (Archer, 1982a, p. 58). Like historical-institutionalists, Archer also sees change in education as an outcome of the relationship between actors and structures (see e.g., Archer, 1982b, p. 455). But Archer's core argument is that this relationship changes in the temporal development of social systems. Archer speaks of "structural elaboration", which creates new institutional contexts for later interactions (Archer, 1982b, p. 458). In contrast to the somewhat open-ended institutionalist approaches, Archer emphasizes that the dynamics of educational systems can be explained by the meaning of educational qualifications for different social actors, whereby this meaning changes according to the principle of structural elaboration in the course of educational expansion.

Thus, the author argues (see e.g., Archer, 1982a) that in many countries at the beginning of this expansion (*take off phase*), groups of actors establish educational offers that serve their own politically or economically motivated interests, to which individual actors initially react atomistically. In the *growth phase*, however, the indifference of the individual actors and their atomistic reactions to the educational offers give way to coordinated behavior, so that expansion – in contrast to the first phase – is determined primarily by growing social demand for education. Then, in the *inflation phase*, educational qualifications increasingly become a basic condition for integration into the labor market, a *conditio sine qua non*, while at the same time losing more and more of their value. In sum, the emergence of education systems, according to Archer, does not in any way correspond to economic structures, but is rather a social field of its own, the dynamics of which are driven by its own success.

Against this theoretical background, the case of Bangladesh will now be examined.

3. Analysis of the case of Bangladesh

This case study starts with a brief, general synthesis of the development of education in the country, and then follows with a chronological analysis of how the VET system evolved, particularly after the VET reforms of 2011.

3.1. Development of general education

Bangladesh, which gained independence from Pakistan in 1971, was long considered one of the poorest countries in the world (Mascarenhas, 1986). However, the country has undergone a major economic and social transformation in recent decades, and, thanks largely to the growth of its clothing industry, is now a lower middle-income country. Nevertheless, stark social inequalities remain, with a considerable share of the population living below the poverty line (Blair, 2020; Sarker et al., 2018).

The territory of present-day Bangladesh had a rich educational history, which cannot be described here in detail. The beginnings of today's formal school system can be traced back to colonial times (Ahmad, 1992). In contrast to other parts of South Asia (e.g., Sri Lanka), basic education expanded only to a very limited extent in the first years of independence from Great Britain, mainly as the ruling elites of Pakistan lacked interest in promoting the economic and social development of the eastern part of their country (Ahmad, 2003; Ahmad, 1992; Maurer, 2012).

With the country's independence in 1971, the importance of educational development was finally recognized at the political level, and from the 1990 s, enrolment rates began to rise rapidly, initially with a focus on primary, then also on secondary education (see e.g., Hossain et al., 2002; World Bank, 1990b). Later, the pace in the growth of the enrolment rates at the secondary level (grades 6–10) and higher secondary level (grades 11–12) decelerated, with net enrolment rates remaining at about 72% and 36% respectively in 2020; the completion rates also continued to be low at both of these levels, 64% and 79% respectively, in 2020 (BANBEIS, 2020). Access to tertiary education has also expanded, although it remains a privilege. The higher the level of education, the greater also the probability of finding employment in the comparatively attractive formal sector of the labor market: in 2016/17, just 10.8% of individuals with a completed primary education as their highest credential were employed in the formal sector, while 19% of lower secondary graduates, 32% of higher secondary graduates, and 48.3% of tertiary graduates enjoyed formal sector employment (BBS, 2018, p. 63).

3.2. Early post-independence development of VET

For many decades, formal VET in today's Bangladesh remained a very small part of the education system, open mainly to those with completed junior secondary education, which requires eight years of schooling. Today, approximately 18% of individuals with these required eight years of education enter formal VET (BANBEIS, 2022).

In fact, VET had very little political significance for a long time: during the Pakistan period, there were only a few secondary level Vocational Training Institutes (VTI) as well as post-secondary level polytechnics, which were all run under the Ministry of Education and were supposed to support the limited industrial development in East Pakistan (Ministry of Labour and Manpower, 1984; Peshkin, 1963). VET enrolment remained low after independence, despite the efforts of early post-independence governments to promote VET for national economic growth (e.g., Government of Bangladesh, 1974), and the creation of practical short-term courses (360 h) by the Ministry of Labour, run by Technical Training Centres (TTC) (BMET, 1979). The 1980 s even saw a decline in the share of secondary level students enrolled in VET, a trend that was mainly the result of the strong growth of general secondary education (CAMPE, 2006; Rafique, 1998). What is more, in the early 1990 s, the absolute number of students enrolled in VET programs started to drop (Rafique, 1994b). This was a result of less funding available for VET (see e.g. World Bank, 1990a), as well as declining demand for VET (as in the case of the VTIs), as it did not open up avenues for educational mobility (Rafique, 1994b).

3.3. Diversification of upper secondary education in the 1990 s

Seeing the dropping demand for VET, policy makers in the mid-1990 s decided to diversify upper secondary education, with practically no support from the international community, which, at that moment, was starting to focus on basic education (see e.g., World Bank, 1990b). The diversification of upper secondary education was particularly promoted by the Bangladesh Technical Education Board (BTEB) (Rafique, 1994a, 1996), the authority with the mandate to define the curricula of all formal VET programs in the country, and to organize the central exams in this sector of the education and training system.

The BTEB introduced a vocational stream consisting of two 2-year education programs – one for years 9 and 10, leading to the Secondary School Certificate Vocational (SSC Voc), and another one for years 11 and 12, leading to the Higher Secondary Certificate Vocational (HSC Voc). As with all other existing formal VET programs, enrolment in SSC Voc required students to have completed junior secondary education. Graduates of the SSC voc program were allowed to enter polytechnic institutes, at which 15% of all seats were allocated to students with this qualification, which provided a considerable incentive to choose the vocational stream. The introduction of this vocational stream had the explicit aim of providing more skilled workers to the labor market, particularly at the technician level, to overcome the dependence of the economy on workers with very limited technical and vocational skills (Planning Commission, 1995). Yet, its main innovation was that it provided opportunities for educational mobility – based on lessons learned from the 1980 s VET reforms, which had led to declining social demand.

The new vocational stream was criticized by donor agencies for being far removed from the requirements of the labor market (see e.g., World Bank, 2006). Yet, in terms of social demand, it soon proved enormously successful: SSC and HSC Vocational became Bangladesh's most popular VET programs, leading to a more than 700% growth in VET enrolment between 1999 and 2011. At the same time, access to the other streams of upper secondary education was handled in a more restrictive way, with the number of SSC graduates barely increasing until 2007. Accordingly, the share of students enrolled in the vocational stream (in relation to all upper secondary students) rose sharply, reaching a peak in 2009, with a 6% share (BANBEIS, 2023).

The existing shorter VET courses continued to be open to those with completed junior secondary education, but did not expand; the aforementioned courses of 360 h were now offered in a more condensed form (4–6 months), yet by 2011, the number of graduates of such courses was virtually the same as the number of SSC Voc graduates – even though SSC Voc was a much more time-consuming and academically demanding program (BANBEIS, 2012).

3.4. The skills development policy 2011

While the international community had only marginally supported VET in Bangladesh in the 1990 s, it rediscovered its interest in it in the early millennium, even before the global financial crisis of 2007/08. With this international support, the country's 2005 Poverty Reduction Strategy Paper proposed further expanding VET (echoing governmental policies from the mid-1990 s). The paper also envisioned making VET more accessible to those who lacked basic education (Government of Bangladesh, 2005), something which had never previously been of prime importance to the ministries or other authorities in charge of VET (see e.g., BTEB, 2005) – and was clearly a priority for donors.

The most important donor-financed intervention that then followed was the EU-funded TVET Reform Project, implemented by the International Labour Organization (ILO) between 2007 and 2015. In particular, it planned to review TVET policies (result 1) as well as to contribute to a “system of TVET qualifications and curricula” that would be “demand-driven, modular and competence-based enabling the underprivileged groups, school drop-outs, and low-literate women to access recognized

skills training” (result 2) ([Delegation of the European Commission to Bangladesh, 2006](#)). This project was of critical importance because it laid the foundations upon which many other donor interventions would build, particularly by paving the way for the 2011 Skills Development Policy (SDP) ([Ministry of Education, 2011](#)).

At the core of the 2011 SDP lay the ambition to implement a national qualifications framework – known as the National Technical and Vocational Qualifications Framework (NTVQF) (since renamed the Bangladesh National Qualifications Framework (BNQF)). This framework was meant to bring the VET programs of different ministries under one umbrella, thereby “increasing options for students by broadening program and progression pathways” ([Ministry of Education, 2011](#)). Of the 8 skill levels it defined, the two lowest ones were of particular relevance for individuals with “limited general knowledge” and a “very limited range of skills and use of tools required to carry out simple tasks” ([Government of Bangladesh, 2013](#)). These are “pre-vocational” levels (pre-voc 1 and 2), leading to the National Pre-Vocation Certificate NPVC 1 and 2, respectively. The introduction of these two levels was to mark a major change in the country’s educational system, as all existing VET programs required, as mentioned above, 8 years of education. In contrast to existing VET qualifications, however, these pre-vocational qualifications were not meant to prepare individuals for labor market entry, but rather enable them to “pursue formal TVET qualifications” ([ILO, 2012a](#)), notably the ones at the first “vocational level” (NTVQF 1). For the pre-vocational levels, the 2011 Skills Development Policy envisioned that the recognition of prior learning (RPL) would play an important role, so that people who had learned vocational skills informally, mostly in the workplace, would also have access to a VET qualification.

The NTVQF was supposed to improve not only the accessibility of VET, but also its alignment with the requirements of the labor market. To this end, competency-based skills standards were to be developed in collaboration with Sector Skills Councils, for which a “CBT Cell” was set up within the BTEB. Clearly, donors hoped that such reforms would lead to a comprehensive revision of all curricula, and potentially even to a replacement of the existing vocational qualifications, in particular SSC and HSC voc. In fact, in an official overview of the country’s VET system in 2015, no mention was made of any of the existing VET programs ([Government of Bangladesh, 2015](#)).

3.5. VET since the adoption of the skills development policy 2011

More than 10 years after the Skills Development Policy was adopted in 2011, it is clear that one of its major goals has not been achieved: VET has not become more accessible.

VET enrolment rates have increased, but most of this has been for programs that require completed junior secondary education – a requirement many adolescents from socio-economically more disadvantaged backgrounds still don’t meet. VET enrolment thus expanded at the level of the SSC voc program, which grew in terms of absolute numbers, though not in terms of its share of upper secondary education. In fact, due to the enormous increase in upper secondary enrolment after 2011, the share of the vocational stream actually decreased from 2011 to 2018, then slightly increased between 2018 and 2021. A much more striking growth, however, was seen in the 360-hour courses. 220,000 candidates completed these courses in 2018, which was far higher than the 140,000 for the SSC voc program. Courses in craft trades (e.g., electrical maintenance) were in particularly high demand, as was the computer science course ([BANBEIS, 2023](#)). While the SSC and HSC voc program is largely publicly financed (even though partly offered by private providers), many of the short courses are offered by private training centers with no public subsidies (even though the qualification is issued by the BTEB), which makes them less accessible to young people from poorer families (Int 2).

In contrast, pre-vocational levels 1 and 2 – the key innovation of the NTVQF for improving access – have barely begun to play a role, with

currently no qualifications at this level being issued (Int 1). In the first years after the reform, some training and assessment centers were set up with donor support, but, given disputes between BTEB and the authority in charge of non-formal education about who would run such centers (and cover the costs) and issue the certificates, these activities could not be sustained (Int 1). In addition, even though it had been a further key ambition when establishing the NTVQF, graduates of the pre-vocational courses were never allowed to access formal VET programs at the next higher levels (e.g., SSC voc or 360 h course) because these continued to require completed junior secondary education (Int 3). Clearly, the responsible authority, BTEB, was never willing to adjust the admission regulations, which undermined the attractiveness of the pre-vocational programs (Int 1) (see also [Maurer and Morshed, 2022](#)).

In contrast to the pre-vocational programs, non-formal VET, i.e., structured training programs that do not lead to a state-recognized qualification, expanded quite strongly after 2011. These programs target disadvantaged groups, are mostly provided by government authorities or non-governmental organizations, and, unlike formal VET programs, do not require completed junior secondary education. Even though there is virtually no official statistical data on this form of training, different reports suggest that, after 2011, the number of beneficiaries of such initiatives grew considerably ([CAMPE, 2019](#)). Yet, the government’s commitment to non-formal VET remained ambiguous: while it was mentioned in the newly introduced Non-Formal Education Act 2014 ([Government of Bangladesh, 2014](#)), the government was still of the view that it was more important to improve access to foundational skills (in particular literacy skills) than vocational or basic entrepreneurial skills (Int 1). As a result, the funding of most non-formal VET programs remained dependent on bi- and multilateral donors or international philanthropy (Int 8).

Private (commercial) non-formal VET also expanded after 2011. Again, there are no official statistics on this. However, our data suggest that two types of private vocationally-oriented training have expanded: one is IT courses that prepare students for office jobs in various economic sectors; the other is sector-specific training, especially for the garment industry (Int 1; 12; 26–30). Due to the size of the industry, the offers have become very differentiated, with very specialized (and often costly) courses for managers and technicians at one of the spectrum (complementing industry-specific higher education programs by private universities), and less expensive courses on basic sewing skills, for poorer people who hope to gain access to the industry, at the other end of the spectrum ([Kalam and Shimu, 2020](#)).

3.6. Interrelations between VET and the labor market

Many existing studies and reports (see e.g., [Haolader et al., 2017](#); [Haolader and Nickolaus, 2012](#); [Khan, 2019](#)) as well as the interviews we conducted with representatives from the world of work (Int 31–34) suggest that the reforms initiated by the 2011 Skills Development Policy did not lead to stronger links between the VET system and the labor market, despite the focus on competency-based training and despite the sector skill councils that have helped to shape skill standards in formal VET since the launch of the TVET Reform Project.

There are different reasons underlying the lack of orientation toward the labor market, but one seems to be particularly key: all state VET qualifications (especially for SSC and HSC voc and the 360 h courses) are based on central examinations conducted by BTEB, in which the assessment of practical vocational skills plays virtually no role at all ([BTEB, 2022](#)). In fact, the introduction of CBT was intended to increase the practical orientation of the exams, but the large weighting of theoretical knowledge in the exams remains central to the credibility of these qualifications (Int 1–4). At the same time, most schools lack essential resources for more practice-oriented VET, especially appropriate infrastructure and equipment and teachers with sector-specific work experience (Int 1; 13–25). Conditions are different in non-formal VET, especially among commercial providers (Int 26–30). In the case of

sewing training, trainees do not attend a course primarily to attain a certificate; rather, they expect to acquire skills that will allow them to pass an entry test at the garment factory (Int 28–30).

This generally low alignment of VET with the requirements of the world of work is related to the fact that formal VET qualifications barely improve access to the labor market. Yet, depending on the segment of the labor market, different levels of educational qualifications play an increasingly important role (Kalam and Shimu, 2020; Shimu, 2021). In the formal private sector, for example, there are no official wage agreements linking wages to specific qualifications, only sector-specific minimum wages set by sectoral tripartite wage boards (BLS, 2015). However, educational qualifications are playing an increasingly important role in recruitment. The decisive factor is the general education level of the job candidates, with varying degrees being required depending on the occupational level (Int 31–34). In the garment industry, at least in the Dhaka area, companies now expect newly recruited seamstresses to have several years of primary school education, and quality controllers are usually expected to have at least a completed junior secondary education or even an SSC (Kalam and Shimu, 2020; Shimu, 2021). When SSC or HSC graduates are hired, their profiles (general or vocational) do not play a role, which can partly be explained by the fact that vocational graduates only make up a small proportion of them, but also by the fact that the practical skills of vocational graduates are perceived to be poor (Int 31–34). Depending on their positioning in the labor market, companies can sometimes afford to make further demands on applicants, including demanding that they have vocational qualifications (mostly awarded by private providers), such as for the short courses for seamstresses mentioned above. Once recruited, all employees receive some form of informal on-the-job training, although the structure of this training varies widely between companies, depending on their size and export orientation (Kalam and Shimu, 2020; Maurer, 2011; Shimu, 2021).

The requirements for employment in the public sector are somewhat different. Based on national standards, educational requirements are set for most positions (e.g., for office clerks), although here, too, the focus is primarily on general education levels. This sector of the labor market contributes significantly to the attractiveness of higher education, since job positions and wage levels are strongly linked to educational credentials (Islam and Hasan, 2020; Rahman and Al-Hasan, 2018). Vocational qualifications are only required for a few positions, such as those within Public Works Departments or vocational schools (Int 6; 9; 11).

In contrast, education and training credentials are not a prerequisite for access to the informal labor market, which is proportionally very important. A large majority of workers in this sector still do not have a completed primary education, but those with a primary education tend to earn more than those without it (Akhi, 2021; BBS, 2018; Yeasin, 2022). Evaluations of (mostly donor-funded) projects that support non-formal skills development have consistently suggested that they improve beneficiaries' positions in the informal labor market (Nakata et al., 2021; Raihan and Shonchoy, 2016). But overall, vocational qualifications – be they formal or non-formal – do not play an important role in the informal labor market, either.

4. Synthesis of findings

4.1. Development of VET in Bangladesh after the 2011 reforms

At the national level, the Skills Development Policy (2011) introduced numerous reforms, in close alignment with what McGrath (2012) called the global VET policy toolkit. The most important outcome of this policy was the creation of a national qualifications framework (NTVQF), which introduced pre-vocational levels to align VET more closely with labor market requirements and make it more accessible to the socially disadvantaged.

In the years that followed, existing forms of formal VET (requiring completion of junior secondary education) continued to grow. The

number of those completing short courses grew particularly rapidly, while the vocational stream at upper secondary level (SSC and HSC vocational), which had contributed to a marked growth in the number of vocational learners in the years before 2011, grew more slowly. However, the share of junior secondary graduates who underwent formal VET remained low. Attainment of non-formal vocational qualifications also increased, particularly through private providers. Despite this growth, vocational qualifications continue to be of little importance in the labor market; hiring and wages are based more on general education qualifications and work experience.

4.2. Influence of donors on improving accessibility of VET

Bi- and multilateral donors had a major influence on the objectives of the Skills Development Policy 2011, and on the implementation provisions in key areas of this policy (e.g., the qualifications framework, competency-based training, RPL); in addition, for several years they financed VET offerings that were directly targeted at disadvantaged social groups. Despite this commitment, the donors had little influence on the implementation of the central objectives of the policy. This is particularly evident in the attempt to make VET more accessible. Courses at pre-vocational levels 1 and 2, which were established for those who had not completed junior secondary school, have not been sustained. For these individuals, therefore, only non-formal offerings are available, and the state-organized non-formal training programs often suffer from an unsustainable financial basis, as they mostly depend on donor-funded projects.

4.3. Explaining these developments

The Skills Development Policy 2011, which aimed to make VET more responsive to the needs of the labor market and contribute to poverty reduction, had little impact on the existing institutions in this part of the education system. From a historical-institutionalist perspective, the new policy can be interpreted as institutional layering. With the introduction of regulations on pre-vocational qualifications or RPL, a new institutional layer was added, one that had the backing of bi- and multilateral donors but lacked the support of the particularly important VET stakeholders in Bangladesh, especially the BTEB, who are of the strong view that access to VET requires a completed junior secondary education.

The existing path of formal VET, which had become established over the decades as an offering at the upper secondary level, was not abandoned; a critical juncture did not occur after 2011. Rather, it was in the 1990s that a critical juncture occurred, when – against the will of donors – a vocational stream was introduced at the upper secondary level (SSC and HSC voc), causing demand for formal VET to rise sharply for the first time. Although that reform was driven by a growing need for skilled technicians, its decisive impact was the access it gave to a new form of an already established upper secondary qualification, thus opening new pathways in the education system. Clearly, this design was a reaction to earlier attempts to shorten VET and give it a more practical orientation, which had failed because of the lack of interest from students. Formal VET thus gained positive feedback primarily through the creation of social demand for upper secondary qualifications (and beyond), and not through its added value for employers. Thus, there never emerged any institutional complementarities between formal VET and the production regimes in the world of work (e.g., regarding recruitment, division of labor and in-company training), which is why neither employers nor trade unions were genuinely interested in achieving the goals of the Skills Development Policy 2011.

Using Archer's perspective, the challenges in implementing the Skills Development Policy 2011 can be interpreted in the larger context of the general expansion of education in Bangladesh. This expansion is still in full swing; the system is in what Archer labeled the "growth phase." Due to the growing number of people with educational qualifications, currently including different levels of secondary education (junior/

senior/higher), such credentials are increasingly important in the labor market, contributing to a further increase in social demand. In contrast to countries with collectively organized or statist VET systems, formal VET had remained a marginal element in this expansion process for a long time. Yet, it began to grow as a consequence of the diversification of upper secondary education – with the introduction of a vocational stream as the second-best option at this level – at a time when only a minority of learners each year continued to upper secondary level; diversification could thus be interpreted as a broadening of access to this level of education.

Still, despite a limited focus on the skills requirements of the world of work, the growth of the upper secondary vocational stream is in line with the growing demand in the labor market for upper secondary graduates. Furthermore, the fact that upper secondary qualifications are increasingly widespread and that many learners, still, do not achieve such a qualification, also contributes to the demand for short courses. These are available as a third-best option for those who aim to obtain a state-recognized qualification after junior secondary education. Despite their being far removed from the skills requirements of the industry, the importance of formal VET qualifications has obviously increased since the introduction of the upper secondary vocational stream, for young people who – by virtue of having a junior secondary qualification – can be considered relatively privileged. The 2011 Skills Development Policy's call to ultimately make VET more accessible to those without completed junior secondary education ran counter to this trajectory of VET in Bangladesh, precisely because formal VET qualifications had come to signal *academic* more than *vocational* competence.

5. Discussion and conclusions

Although some of the developments under study in this article are specific to Bangladesh, its findings as well as its theoretical approach are relevant beyond this case: it attempts – with the help of a historical-institutionalist approach and the work of Archer – to explain the development of VET systems in the context of the expansion of education systems as a whole. From this perspective, the goal of making VET more accessible and inclusive ("VET for all") was not achieved because, in the context of educational expansion, formal VET had become an alternative form of upper secondary education that provided access to higher education. This finding does not challenge Foster's classic thesis: there is undoubtedly large social demand for higher education in Bangladesh; yet, this paper shows that this demand does not impede the development of VET, so long as VET is able to provide graduates with opportunities to proceed to higher education, a phenomenon that is also emphasized by Aldinucci et al. (2021). In fact, a key element of formal VET in Bangladesh, the upper secondary vocational stream, could even be understood as a policy response to Foster's "vocational school fallacy" thesis, a second-best option at the upper secondary level that leads less directly to the highest credentials in the education system, but makes them more permeable/accessible, and is chosen primarily because of this. Undoubtedly, the development of vocational competence in the proper sense has not, so far, been the focus of such an offer.

With this reading, our paper distinguishes itself from political economy interpretations of VET development in terms of the relationships between governments, employers, and unions. These interpretations have been put forward in the recent political science literature dealing mainly with OECD countries (Bonoli and Emmenegger, 2022; Bussemeyer and Trampusch, 2012; Thelen, 2004), as well as in Ashton et al.'s (2000) study of VET in LMICs. Unlike the latter, our analysis of Bangladesh does not take a functionalist view, because the development of VET clearly does not depend on either economic policy or the economic structure of the country. Moreover, in the case of Bangladesh, the disjuncture of the VET system described by Ashton et al. manifests in a different form: firstly, while public formal VET does not target the socially privileged, who prepare for university entrance through the non-vocational upper secondary streams, it does target

those who, by having completed junior secondary education, have come quite far in the education system by national standards. Thus, its pursuit of poverty reduction is more rhetoric than reality. Secondly, there is indeed a growing private, commercial VET offering, but it is highly differentiated: cheap courses can be found for the poorest, and expensive courses can be found for future professionals and experienced employees.

This analysis also differs somewhat from the postcolonial position (e.g., Allais and Wedekind (2020)). Of course, the country's colonial past continues to shape Bangladesh's education system today, and its economic structure cannot be understood without looking at its positioning in the global division of labor. Moreover, the objectives of the 2011 Skills Development Policy, which were not aligned with the interests of key actors in the country's VET system, are a good example of what Allais and Wedekind call "policy posturing." Nevertheless, the structural development of VET in Bangladesh is beyond the direct influence of bilateral and multilateral donors: its expansion occurred essentially against their will.

The findings on Bangladesh put into perspective the possibilities of reducing poverty through aid for VET, since, firstly, the use of such aid would need the support of key VET actors and, secondly, vocational qualifications barely play a role in many parts of the labor market – particularly those parts that do not require comprehensive general education. Furthermore, it is questionable whether it makes sense to formally define VET as a central field of development policy, as long as vocational qualifications, despite enormous efforts, continue to signal academic competence more than practical competence, and as long as there remain considerable challenges and inequalities in basic education. Admittedly, our view contrasts with the dominant global discourse on education, where hybrid forms of VET – those that prepare for the world of work as well as for higher education – are seen as particularly relevant (UNESCO, 2021). Yet, if one follows further down this path, one relies on education that is vocational in name only, and contributes very little to vocational competence in the true sense of the word (as in the case of the vocational stream in Bangladesh).

Thus, we do not fundamentally doubt the potential of VET to contribute to actual vocational learning, and through this, to economic and social development in LMICs. But such relevant VET training necessarily requires a sectorial or occupational focus, and, depending on the skill level, a stronger emphasis on practice or theory, but undoubtedly always both. So far, in Bangladesh and in many other countries, private providers often succeed better in designing such training. If the state (with the possible support of development aid) also gets involved in this area, then it might make sense to do so at a time when sector-specific skill formation and production regimes can still be strongly influenced by such interventions – as other experiences from South Asia show.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

study conception and design: author 1, data collection: author 2; author 3, analysis and interpretation of results: author 1; author 2; author 3, draft manuscript preparation: author 1, All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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